

REVIEW: RENE DESCARTES'S MEDITATIONS ON FIRST PHILOSOPHY

by

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In this review, a summary of the meditations on the first philosophy of Rene Descartes and key elements of his argument are discussed. His arguments are critiqued from a Christian perspective.

Summary

In his meditations on “first philosophy,” Descartes attempted to demonstrate the existence of God and the distinction between the human soul (mind) and the body. In the first meditation, he attempted to doubt everything that he believed formerly. He found that his senses deceived him time after time. He recognized the need for demolishing all indubitable things and starting all over from the foundations. He reasoned that the studies which are dependent on composite things including physics, astronomy, medicine, etc., are dubitable. Studies like arithmetic, geometry and other studies are undoubtful and certain. If God is the creator of all things, he never allows deception in his creation. Therefore, he concluded that there must be a malevolent demon that deceives him. All of his experiences and senses are the delusions of dreams created by the demon.

In the second meditation, he explained the nature of the human mind and how it is better than the body. He argued that he cannot doubt his own existence because he is the one who is thinking. He exists as long as he thinks, and he is truly a thinking thing. Though corporeal things are dubitable, the capacity to imagine them is part of his thinking, therefore it cannot be false. He gave an illustration of the nature and imagination of wax. All the changes in the wax like color, textures, and fragrance are perceived through his senses and dubitable. However, the nature of wax remains unchanged and is perceived by his mind (intellect). He concluded that if he could perceive

a piece of wax distinctly, then he must be true, and his self-awareness must be evident. His intellect is the one that perceives everything, even the things which are not perceived by his senses.

In the third meditation, he argued for the existence of God. He argued that there are inequality and distinction in his perception of things outside him. The ideas that represent the substances have a more objective reality than the ideas that represent accidents. The ideas that give understanding about an infinite and supreme God have more objective reality (in our mind) than the ideas that represent finite substances (in our mind). It is possible that objective realities also exist outside the mind. God is infinite, eternal, immutable, independent, supremely powerful, and the creator of all things that exist. As a finite being, he cannot originate from the idea of an infinite being in his mind unless it comes from an infinite being. Therefore, God necessarily exists. It is God who placed the idea of a perfect being in us, it is the mark of the craftsman stamped on his work.

In the fourth meditation, he explained the distinction between truth and falsity. In this meditation, he reflected on the source of deception. Since God is all perfect, he never deceives, and he never gives faculties of judgment to make mistakes. The faculties of the human mind, imagination, and memory are weak and finite. The cause of the error lies in the nature of the finitude of man. He did not complain that God withheld something from him. Instead, he expressed his gratitude for God's benevolence.

In the fifth meditation, he explained the essence of material things and he argued for the existence of God. He observed that many ideas in the world are true, immutable in nature, and independent of his mind. For example, the idea of a triangle is immutable and eternal, which is not dependent on his mind. Despite his previous dilemma about the existence of corporeal things, he always held that shapes, numbers, and mathematics are truths. Just as he conceived of the idea of shape or number, he also conceived of the idea of a supremely perfect being. If the mathematical truths are certain, then the existence of God must be certain. If God exists and if he is not a deceiver, then everything he perceives clearly and distinctly should be true. All of his knowledge is

dependent upon his awareness of the true God. Once God's existence is established, it is possible to achieve the full and certain knowledge of intellectual and corporeal things.

In the sixth meditation, he explained the existence of material things and the distinction between the mind (soul) and body. He examined the distinction between imagination and pure understanding. When the mind understands something, it looks inward and inspects one of the ideas within itself, but when it imagines, it looks towards the body to conform to an idea of the mind or to perceive by the senses. He is a thinking, non-extended thing. He has a body, which is an extended, non-thinking thing. He is distinct from the body, and he can exist without it. He is closely joined with his body to form unity. Since the nature of man is the combination of mind and body, it is possible for him to err. The faculties of imagination and sensory perception are modes of thing, but they are not the actual substance. It is possible for him to understand himself as a whole without those faculties.

Key Elements of the Argument

The argument of Descartes consists of three elements including methodic doubt, the primacy of mind and mind-body dualism, and the existence of God based on a priori reasoning. First, Descartes employed a methodic doubt to know about the certainty of the realities. It is also known as metaphysical or hyperbolic doubt. He attempted to doubt everything that is uncertain. All the sensory experience must be doubted because it makes errors. However, he could not doubt a few things. First, he cannot doubt himself because he is the one who is thinking and doubting. Second, he did not doubt the truthfulness of mathematical formulations, shapes, and forms because they exist outside of his perception. Third, he did not doubt the existence of God because it is possible for God to exist if mathematical ideas exist. Second, he argued for the primacy of the mind and gave a notion of mind-body dualism. Man is essentially a thinking being. He asserted that "I am a thing that thinks" (35). He argued that the mind (soul) is a non-extending and thinking thing. On the other hand, the body is an extended and non-thinking thing. He argued that man exists apart from the body (54). Third, he argued for the existence of God based on the

craftsmanship argument and ontological argument. In the third meditation, he argued for the existence of God based on the mark that he placed in us, the very idea of the supreme being in our mind. In the fifth meditation, he provided a modified ontological argument in which he argued that God's existence is self-evident just as the truths about mathematics.

Critique of the Argument

Descartes attempted to defend the existence of God and demonstrate the distinction between mind and body on the scholastic philosophical foundations. He provided his arguments as a Christian who believes in the true God—one supreme, eternal, omnipotent, omnibenevolent, and all-perfect God and creator of all things. Though he sincerely attempted to argue for the existence of God and solve the dilemma of mind-body distinction, he failed to adhere to biblical principles and further advanced skepticism and subjectivism. His method of metaphysical doubt and his arguments for mind-body dualism are incompatible with the Christian worldview. Though he argued from a Christian perspective, he sparked the intellectual movement that doubt all the foundations of human life including the premise of God's existence.

First, his methodological doubt and his guiding principles are inconsistent with the Christian worldview. If Descartes was consistent with his argument of God's truthfulness, he would not entertain a doubt about God's word. After the creation, God clearly confirmed that all that he had made was good (Gen 1:31). All of the creation was true, real, and ordered. There is no legitimate reason for questioning the existence of creation, sensations, and perceptions. If a Christian presupposes the authority of scriptures and embraces the biblical worldview, he must start his study of metaphysics and epistemology from the account of Genesis. According to the Christian worldview, God created the world in the beginning (Gen 1:1), he created man in his image and blessed him (Gen 1:27-28), and he saw that all that he had made was good (Gen 1:31). The man is expected to obey God and be faithful to him. However, the corruption of sin entered through the doubt (Gen 3:1-7). Adam and Eve sinned against God by not believing his word.

Instead of grounding his principles in the scriptures, Descartes pursued a path of doubt in his philosophical deliberations. He clearly neglected to ground his metaphysics in the scriptures.

Second, the argument of mind-body dualism is inconsistent with the scriptures. Descartes understood the limitations of the human body and explained the primacy of the mind (soul). However, he failed to provide an authentic account of human anthropology. God created man as one entity with a body and soul (holistic dualism). The immaterial soul exists in an intermediate state between death and resurrection (Luke 23:42-43). There is no indication of the superiority of mind over body. All of God's creation was good including material bodies (Gen 1:31). Humans are created as holistic beings with a body and animated spirit (Gen 2:7). The hope of bodily resurrection emphasizes the importance of a physical body (1 Cor 15:35-58). The account of creation and the notion of bodily resurrection reject the notions of Cartesian dualism.

Third, the arguments for God's existence suffer a lack of philosophical coherence and biblical support because of his methodological doubt. In his philosophical method, the arguments for the existence of God are grounded in the ability of the mind to conceive the idea of the supreme being and mathematical truths. However, once the seeker pursues the path of doubt, he is not restricted to escaping this doubt and later questions the very existence of his mind, its comprehension of the truth, and the existence of God. Cartesian arguments inevitably lead to skepticism. The scriptures do not teach the autonomy of rationality. Instead, proper rationality begins with the acknowledgment of God (Prov 9:10).

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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